

Photometric filter characteristics for GAIA

L. Lindegren, E. Høg & J. Knude

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ABSTRACT. We give provisional specifications of filter characteristics for the GAIA Broad Band Photometer (BBP) and Medium Band Photometer (MBP). The transmittance curves for the BBP are triangular or bell-shaped, as has been found suitable for chromaticity calibration.

1 Introduction

In GAIA-LL-039 it was shown that overlapping broadband filters of triangular or bell-shaped transmittance curves are to be preferred over standard, near-rectangular passbands for the GAIA Broad-Band Photometer (BBP), at least from the viewpoint of chromaticity calibration. Provisional tests made by the Vilnius group indicate that such filters are also acceptable for astrophysics (TBC).

In order to investigate the manufacturing feasibility of such filter curves, a provisional specification is derived in this note. The specification of the transmittance curve is given in the form of an upper and a lower envelope.

Corresponding specifications for the Medium Band Photometer (MBP) are also given, using the four Strömrgren *wby* bands as representative examples of the final selection of MBP bands.

We include some astrophysical arguments, e.g. why the tolerances of some medium-band filters may have to be different for the two edges (see Note 3 to Table 2).

2 Envelope for triangular or bell-shaped BBP filters

One tentative conclusion from GAIA-LL-039 is that the triangular shape *per se* is not the crucial factor; e.g. the same number of overlapping bell-shaped passbands can give equivalent advantages. Thus we define the idealised transmittance envelope in such a way as to include both a triangular and a bell-shaped curve having the same FWHM (Fig. 1).

FIGURE 1. Proposed envelope of the generic bandpass shape to be used for the GAIA Broad Band Photometer (BBP). The dashed curves show the transmittances of the triangular and bell-shaped passbands considered in GAIA-LL-039. The solid lines define upper and lower envelopes that encompass both filter shapes.

3 Specifications for BBP and MBP filters

3.1 General specifications

Table 1 summarises the filter specifications, except for the transmittance curves, which are specified in the next Section.

3.2 Normalised transmittance curves

The wavelengths and transmittances in this Section refer to the beams and operating temperatures specified in Table 1.

For any filter transmittance curve $T(\lambda)$ we define the *normalised transmittance* as $t(\lambda) = T(\lambda)/T_{\max}$, where T_{\max} is the maximum of $T(\lambda)$.

The transmittance curve is specified in three steps:

1. The normalised transmittance curve should approximate the nominal bandpass defined by the four *nominal parameters*: central wavelength λ_0 , bandwidth $\Delta\lambda$ (FWHM), and edge slopes $\delta\lambda_1$ and $\delta\lambda_2$; see Fig. 2. Actually, it is desirable that the ‘corners’ of the passband are somewhat rounded, but they should stay within the boundaries set by the tolerance parameters below.
2. The *tolerance parameters* ε_1 , ε_2 , λ_{\min} and λ_{\max} define an envelope within which the actual normalised transmittance curve should lie (apart from the leakage described below).

TABLE 1. General filter specifications.

Property	BBP	MBP
beam	f/33	f/4.2 (TBC)
operating temperature	TBD	TBD
size	TBD	TBD
minimum clear aperture	TBD	TBD
maximum thickness ¹	8–10 mm (TBC)	5 mm (TBC)
flatness ²	$\lambda/4$ per inch (TBC)	$\lambda/4$ per inch (TBC)
parallelism ²	1 arcmin (TBC)	1 arcmin (TBC)
scratch-dig ³	60–40 (TBC)	60–40 (TBC)
A/R coating	both sides < 1% (TBC)	both sides < 1% (TBC)

1. A maximum thickness of 5 mm for the MBP is highly desirable. But we are aware that the UV filter may need up to 8–10 mm because of a colour filter required to block the red leak.
2. Specification as used in high-precision ground-based photometry
3. As used in ground-based photometry. We do not know what it really means except that it is according to specifications in MIL-O-13830A, DIN 3140.

FIGURE 2. This diagram defines the nominal passband shape in terms of the four wavelengths $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4$; or equivalently by the central wavelength λ_0 , bandwidth $\Delta\lambda$ (FWHM), and edge slopes $\delta\lambda_1, \delta\lambda_2$. The normalised transmittance should approximate this general shape, although somewhat rounded ‘corners’ are actually desirable. Tolerances for the shape are defined by the additional parameters in Fig. 3.

FIGURE 3. This diagram defines the tolerances for the shape of the normalised transmittance, i.e. the actual shape should fall within the boundaries (envelope) defined by the straight-line segments. The two parallel lines separated by ε_1 and ε_2 have the same slope as the nominal edges in Fig. 2, and are centred on these. Below λ_{\min} and above λ_{\max} the transmittance should not exceed the blocking factor T_1 . **Note:** The description of tolerances by the broken lines in the figure is quite simple, but the real transmissions are smooth curves. The elbows may therefore impose unnecessarily strict requirements and cause difficulties in the manufacturing or higher than necessary cost. Such deviations from the formal specifications should therefore be discussed as the need arises.

3. The *transmittance parameters* T_0 and T_1 define minimum requirements for how well the light is transmitted inside the filter band, and rejected outside the band. The maximum transmittance T_{\max} should be at least T_0 . Outside of $[\lambda_{\min}, \lambda_{\max}]$ the transmittance (leakage) should be at most T_1 .

The detailed passbands for BBP and MBP are as yet undefined and we can therefore only give representative examples of what they could look like. For the BBP, we have chosen the system S5LOG, which gave the best performance for chromaticity calibration of the systems studied in GAIA-LL-039. For the MBP, we have chosen the four bands of the classical Strömgren *uvby* system, which are fairly representative of the many different bands considered for the MBP. The various passband parameters are given in Table 2.

The nominal passband can also be specified by means of the four wavelengths λ_1 , λ_2 , λ_3 , λ_4 , related to the previously defined parameters through

$$\lambda_1 = \lambda_0 - \frac{1}{2}\Delta\lambda - \frac{1}{2}\delta\lambda_1 \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda_2 = \lambda_0 - \frac{1}{2}\Delta\lambda + \frac{1}{2}\delta\lambda_1 \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda_3 = \lambda_0 + \frac{1}{2}\Delta\lambda - \frac{1}{2}\delta\lambda_2 \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda_4 = \lambda_0 + \frac{1}{2}\Delta\lambda + \frac{1}{2}\delta\lambda_2 \quad (4)$$

TABLE 2. Parameters for the transmittance profiles. λ_0 = central wavelength; $\Delta\lambda$ = FWHM; $\delta\lambda_1$, $\delta\lambda_2$ = edge slopes as in Fig. 2; λ_1 – λ_4 wavelengths as in Fig. 2; ε_1 , ε_2 = tolerances on the passband edges as in Fig. 3; λ_{\min} , λ_{\max} = interval where significant transmittance may occur, see Fig. 3. T_0 = minimum transmittance at maximum; T_1 = maximum transmittance (leakage) outside of $[\lambda_{\min}, \lambda_{\max}]$. All wavelengths are in nm.

Filter	Nominal parameters								Tolerances				Transm.	
	λ_0	$\Delta\lambda$	$\delta\lambda_1$	$\delta\lambda_2$	λ_1	λ_2	λ_3	λ_4	ε_1	ε_2	λ_{\min}	λ_{\max}	T_0	T_1
BBP-1	300	190	167	167	121	289	311	479	23	23	110	490	0.90	10^{-4}
BBP-2	410	261	231	231	164	395	425	656	32	32	149	671	0.90	10^{-4}
BBP-3	561	358	315	315	225	539	583	897	44	44	205	917	0.90	10^{-4}
BBP-4	768	484	430	430	311	741	795	1225	60	60	280	1256	0.90	10^{-4}
BBP-5	1050	667	588	588	422	1011	1089	1678	81	81	383	1717	0.90	10^{-4}
MBP-u	350	30	22	22	324	346	354	376	5	5	297	403	0.90	10^{-4}
MBP-v	411	18	12	11	396	408	414	426	1	2	384	438	0.90	10^{-4}
MBP-b	468	18	12	11	453	465	471	483	2	2	441	495	0.90	10^{-4}
MBP-y	548	23	12	12	531	543	554	566	2	2	518	578	0.90	10^{-4}

Notes:

1. The five BBP passbands form a geometric progression: the wavelengths in BBP- $(n + 1)$ are a factor 1.368 greater than in BBP- n .
2. The passband shapes outside the CCD sensitivity region (300–1050 nm, TBC) are uncritical.
3. MBP-v is an example where ε_1 and ε_2 may be different, here because the Ca II H & K are included in the passbands. If it is considered that the photometry benefits from their inclusion, ε_1 should be 1 nm, instead of 2 nm, whereas ε_2 is not so critical.